

samples were stored at 20 °C and 75% relative humidity after infestation. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with four replications.

Resistance was evaluated on three parameters: emerging adults, susceptibility index (SI), and weight loss. The emerging adults were removed each day and counted. Seed weight loss was calculated by weighing seed before and after the experiment.

SI was based on the formula

$$SI = \frac{\text{natural log number of emerging adults}}{\text{average development period}} \times 100$$

Susceptibility was scored as % emerging adults where resistant (R) = <10%, moderately resistant (MR) = 10-20%, and susceptible = >20%.

Twelve of 44 BPH-resistant rice varieties tested were rated R and 15 were MR to AGM (see table). The new variety Hong Yuan, which is a cross of the good agronomic variety Hong Zhan and resistant donor Suweon 294, is R to BPH and MR to AGM. Hong Yuan yielded an average 6 t/ha, indicating that the resistance was heritable and easily recombined with other agronomic traits. ■

Stress tolerance—excess water

Plant elongation at three seedling ages in some rice varieties

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Experiments using three seedling ages (2, 3, and 4 wk with 9, 21, and 21 entries, respectively) were laid out in a completely randomized design with three replications to assess variation in plant elongation ability induced by flooding. The objective was to select the most

appropriate seedling age for use in work on the genetics of elongation ability.

Seedlings were submerged for 7 d in 100 cm of water in a glasshouse tank. Plant height was recorded before and after flooding, and the difference was used to calculate plant elongation.

Seedlings in each age group survived. Entries differed significantly in plant elongation. Percent increase in elongation after flooding was highest in the 2-wk seedlings (see table), perhaps because older seedlings were taller than younger

ones and needed comparatively less elongation to survive at the 100-cm flooding depth. Leaf sheaths and blades contributed considerably to plant elongation (data not presented).

To compare the relevance of results, we used previous knowledge that IR11141-6-1-4 and IR11288-B-B-69-1 are elongating modern varieties (MVs), whereas IR36, IR42, BKNFR76106-16-0-1, and FR13A are nonelongating MVs. Better selection of elongating MVs and nonelongating MVs was obtained from the 4-wk treatment. The difference in average elongation between these groups was greater at 4 wk (6.3 cm) than at 3 wk (3.0 cm) (see table). ■

Plant elongation at 3 seedling ages following 7 d of submergence.

Variety	Plant elongation (cm) at			Elongation score in previous test
	2 wk	3 wk	4 wk	
Elongating types				
Saingar	-	37	13	1
Barogar	-	37	20	1
LMN111	-	42	21	1
Jalmagna	24	27	36	1
NDGR407	25	-	-	1
Chakia 59	-	34	16	3
IR40905-11-3-1-5-3-3	-	25	16	3
NC492	-	28	20	3
Baisbish	26	23	21	3
NDGR150	22	22	7	5
FRG15	-	24	9	5
Madhukar	-	20	10	5
NDGR207	15	21	12	5
Elongating MVs				
IR11141-6-1-4	17	16	12	5
IR28273-R-R-R-39-28	-	17	18	5
IR11288-B-B-69-1	13	12	11	5
Nonelongating MVs				
Ghoghari	-	18	10	7
Shayma	-	15	9	7
IR42 (susceptible check)	14	9	8	9
FR13A	-	13	5	9
BKNFR76106-16-0-1	-	8	5	9
IR36	11	9	7	9
Mean increase (%)	46.9	37.9	18.7	
CV (%)	9.2	17.6	25.0	

Optimum water depth for testing fast elongating deepwater rice (DWR) varieties

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We conducted an experiment to determine the optimum water depth for testing the ability for fast elongation in

Table 1. Analysis of variance for percent elongation in 12 varieties at 5 water depths and control.

SV	DF	MS ^a
Replications	2	32.0 ns
Water depth (d)	5	3013.1**
Error (a)	10	18.6
Varieties (v)	11	1861.0**
Depth × variety (d × v)	55	113.9**
Error (b)	132	17.8

CV (a) = 18.0%, CV (b) = 17.6%

** = significant at 1% level, ns = not significant.

Table 2. Varietal means for percent elongation at various water depths.

Variety	Elongation (%)						Variety mean
	80 cm	90 cm	100 cm	110 cm	120 cm	Control (no water)	
<i>Nonelongating dwarf</i>							
BKNFR76106	7.9 h	7.5 e	9.2 d	11.4 e	7.7 f	2.8 b	7.8
IR42	18.4 fg	16.6 d	21.3 c	17.9 de	10.8 hi	3.7 ab	14.8
<i>Nonelongating tall</i>							
IR28273-R-R-R-29-38-2-3-3	13.9 gh	8.2 e	13.5 d	12.0 e	18.0 fgh	7.9 ab	12.3
NDGR207	34.5 bc	25.1 c	27.7 c	32.8 c	19.0 efg	4.0 ab	13.9
<i>Elongating MV</i>							
IR11141-6-1-4	25.9 de	23.9 c	24.8 c	18.1 de	23.2 def	5.4 ab	20.2
IR11288-B-B-69-1	21.4 ef	19.7 ed	28.7 c	15.1 e	15.4 gh	9.1 ab	16.8
IR40905-11-3-1-5-3-2	19.9 efg	22.5 cd	28.0 c	24.7 d	17.8 fgh	9.9 b	19.5
Bhatin	32.6 cd	40.7 a	38.3 b	35.9 bc	32.3 bc	4.5 ab	30.7
LMN111	48.0 a	44.8 a	48.4 a	37.4 bc	25.8 cde	9.4 ab	35.6
<i>Fast elongating</i>							
Baisbish	38.6 bc	41.3 a	41.8 a	50.3 a	35.6 ab	2.9 ab	36.2
Barogar	40.5 b	33.9 b	45.8 a	41.8 b	29.8 bcd	9.1 ab	33.5
Kalaungi	37.3 bc	32.5 b	51.5 a	42.1 b	41.8 a	10.9 a	36.0
Depth mean	28.2	26.4	31.5	28.3	23.1	6.1	23.9

DWR seedlings. We classified 12 varieties as nonelongating dwarf, nonelongating tall, elongating modern variety (MV), elongating tall, and fast elongating. Plants were raised in 5-cm-

deep plastic pots, having 5-cm² surface area. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with three replications. Five water depths were in the main plots and the 12 entries were in the subplots.

Elongation of deepwater rice during horizontal orientation of shoots in shallow water

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Elongating and nonelongating varieties were grown in three sets in completely randomized block design with three replications in tanks at IRRI. Plants were spaced at 30 cm with 90 cm between rows to prevent plants from shading each other. Elongated internode number was <1 and length <5 cm for all varieties at the beginning of the treatments.

In the first set of experiments, the water level was raised to 50 cm 6 wk after seeding. The tank was full at this level. A horizontally placed iron bar was used to submerge all leaves that were above the water. The bar was moved across the top of the tank 2-3 times/wk to stimulate kneeing and to keep plants

completely submerged as they grew. By the end of the experiment, the bar had been moved about 60 cm from the initial position. Using this procedure, all plants, including nonelongating varieties, were submerged but stayed alive.

The second set of the varieties were maintained in an upright position (URP) in 50 cm water and the third set was used as control without deep water treatment. Internode number and length were recorded on 10 randomly selected plants/replication from the three treatments.

Varieties in the horizontally placed (HP) treatment differed significantly in internode length (Table 1), with highest values recorded in Jalmagna, Baisbish, and NDGR417 followed by NDGR150, IR11288-B-B-69-1, and NDGR207 (Table 2). Internode length was minimum for IR42 and IR36. A similar trend in internode length occurred in URP treatment (Table 2). However, HP plants

We submerged 3-wk-old seedlings in a concrete tank where water depths of 80, 90, 100, 110, and 120 cm were maintained using a stair arrangement. Water depth was measured from the soil surface of the pots to the water surface. Percent elongation was calculated.

Varieties differed significantly in percent elongation at various water depths (Table 1). Elongation rate was greatest in Baisbish, Kalaungi, LMN111, and Barogar at almost all water depths. IR11141-6-1-4 and IR40905-11-3-1-5-3-2 showed moderate elongation (Table 2).

We recorded relatively more elongation at 100 cm for floating and DWR varieties. The overall percent elongation, irrespective of variety, was also highest (31.5%) at the 100 cm water depth. For genetic studies, 100 cm of water appears to be deep enough to test for elongation ability at an early stage.

The trend for decreasing elongation at 100 and 120 cm water depths may be due to the inability of plants to emerge from these depths. Alternatively, other adverse factors may exist that affect the ability of plants to elongate in deep water (120 cm) but not in shallow water (80-100 cm). Lower light irradiance could be one factor; this requires further experimentation. ■

had significantly greater internode length relative to those in URP (Table 2) and the control. NDGR207 elongated similarly under both treatments, possibly because of its tall but relatively nonelongating nature.

Table 1. Analysis of variance for internode length (cm) and number of internodes.

Sources of variation	DF	Mean sum of squares ^a	
		Internode length (cm)	Internodes (no.)
Treatment	26	2756.8**	11.3**
Main factor (M)	2	2940.2**	46.3**
Subfactor (S)	8	8014.1**	21.3**
M × S	16	105.3**	1.9**
Error	54	29.9	0.3
CV (%)		7.1	8.1

** = significant at 1% level.